

Linguistic Features of the Translation of Military Terminology

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Annotation:

The purpose of this article is to examine how military terminology and phraseological units from the English language are translated into Uzbek. Methods for choosing equivalents and the pragmatic quirks of translating phraseological units are provided.

Keywords: Tracing, Phraseological Unit, Professionalisms, Terminology, Term, Military Sphere.

One of the primary challenges in the art of translation is the translation of military terminology in written translations, the transfer of critical military-political information and interrogations, and the incorporation of all language "innovations" into oral speech that is then written down. Sometimes, notions are limited to the spoken form. When nations collaborate with one another in the areas of military education and training, experience-sharing between armed forces, and military personnel training, a variety of oral communication issues, including this one, come up. To carry out and enhance their professional military operations and complete professional communication responsibilities, military personnel require foreign language proficiency, much like other experts. This is crucial for the growth and fortification of the military.

Words used primarily by members of a certain profession or scientific subject are referred to as special vocabulary. Terms designating scientific, technological, military, etc. topics are included in the unique vocabulary [Paluanova Kh.D., 2016].

The layer of particular vocabulary comprises terminology as well as professionalism. The phrase is mostly employed in a narrowly defined area of human endeavor or science. Professionalisms are more frequently employed in the casual conversation of those who represent a certain specialization or profession. When it comes to linguistic style, the phrases are utilized in the official style, while the professionalism is more neutral and leans toward speaking in a colloquial manner. They are sometimes referred to as semi-official terms used by similar profession. It can be the language of

doctors, teachers, musicians, military personnel, etc. [B.Strang, 2009, p. 414]. Here is what J. writes about this. Austin: "... all kinds of particular concepts, such as jargon, argot, special language, slang, and the like, do not have the necessary terminological rigor of definitions. They are often used indiscriminately, substitute for each other or receive ambiguous, sometimes mutually exclusive interpretations" [J.Austin, 2008; 440].

Many times, professionalism is seen as the result of the unique inventiveness of certain social and industrial-professional native speaker groups [Shevchuk V.N., 2006; 191-192]. Professionalisms occupy a unique stratum of language that is between neutral ordinary words and terms. Linguists working in the fields of sociolinguistics, lexicography, stylistics, and cognitive science become more interested in them. N.Dittmar draws the conclusion that figurative terminology, which is abundant in colloquial phrases, pertains "to the lexical sphere of professional jargon" after studying the English phraseological units used in the sports industry [N.Dittmar, 2009; 321]. The semantics of words is a very small subset of the lexical and semantic area of professions. This discrepancy is explained by the fact that professionals have a broader range of realities than those represented by, say, a rather small circle of realities.

Looking at professional language from a stylistics perspective, we can say that most of the time it lacks expressiveness. Military staff members employ unregulated vocabulary in their speeches, communications, and diaries [Bates, 2006; 211]. Professional language also avoids expressing an opinionated or subjective stance toward the subject of the speech. Professionalisms, therefore, serve solely as nominative phrases. There are only some literature genres where colloquial professionalism exists. They belong to a conversational-familiar style and frequently carry a negative meaning. Military phraseological units and phrases may begin as popular idioms before becoming officially recognized as terms [Akhmedov O.S., 2016; 133]. There are two types of phraseological units employed in the military domain: 1) with elements of professionalism and 2) arising on the basis of everyday vocabulary. Military stable phrases are characterized by a narrow sphere of use, since military vocabulary belongs to a rather narrow circle of speakers, is used and understood only by military staff [Shevchenko, Mitchell, Ignatov, 2016; 68]. The scope of the use of professional vocabulary is quite limited, although it is included in the system of literary language [Bolinger, 2005; 114].

It is the translator's responsibility to correctly and completely translate the content, free from mistakes and distortions. To ascertain the precise meaning of a phrase and how it is conveyed during translation, one must examine the process by which military terminology are formed. Of course, in an interpretation scenario involving considerable time limits, this understanding is especially important for a military interpreter. To swiftly become familiar with and comprehend the problems, a translator must be aware of the following word construction techniques. Syntactic words are the most prevalent; these are created by combining pre-existing signals in the language; affixation, calcification, word composition, reduction, and conversion are the most effective methods.

I. Rasulov believes that tracing paper is one of the most adequate ways to translate military vocabulary [Rasulov And, 1977; 66]. In addition to tracing paper, affixation, composition, morphological, phonological and lexico-semantic methods of translation are used to translate military vocabulary. The term "tracing paper" appeared in the late XIX-early XX century. Sh. Bally first introduced this term and interpreted it as follows: "Tracing paper is a borrowed word from another language" [Bally Sh, 1961; 67].

It should be noted that when using the tracing (calque) paper method in the translation of military vocabulary, a foreign (borrowed) word can be used, which undergoes phonetic processing of the translation language and is further used in it. Therefore, there is a distinction between full tracing

paper method and partial tracing paper. For example, the gallicism chief of staff first entered the Russian language as "chief of staff", and then into the Uzbek language as "shtab boshligi".

So, English phraseological units of the military sphere of use, denoting various types of weapons and military equipment, usually do not have Uzbek equivalents and analogues. When translating such expressions from English into Uzbek, the name of this weapon in Uzbek should be selected. It follows from this that a military phraseology in translation can be transformed into a military term in the absence of such a phraseological expression in the target language.

Therefore, a study of military words and how to translate them from English into Uzbek was done for this article. The majority of military jargon pertains to the phrases themselves; that is, a term that has a single meaning and is not ambiguous.

The speech of prisoners of war may be fully translated into Uzbek by using their exact correspondences. However, keep in mind that word choice and meaning—even in military contexts—are strongly influenced by the surrounding circumstances. Errors in the translation of military terms can lead to significant distortion and change of meaning. Combat documents, regulations, instructions and technical descriptions, where the accuracy of the translation of military terms is a prerequisite, also often have to be translated during interrogation. In order to avoid such mistakes, the interpreter needs to constantly improve his knowledge of military terminology, modern realities of the development of military science and technology, as well as the military-political situation in the world. Summing up the above, it should be noted that translating military discourse is not an easy and extremely responsible task. The translator of this profile is obliged not only to demonstrate excellent knowledge of native and foreign languages, but also to understand the realities of domestic and foreign weapons, the principles of military service, to know the history and structure of the army of his native country and the army of the enemy.

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